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DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF EMULGEL FOR WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The study was designed with the aim to evaluate metformin and atorvastatin for its wound Healing activity. Two different formulations of Metformin emulgel and atorvastatin emulgel were formulated using Design expert 9.0. The drugs were first screened for its solubility in various surfactant, co-surfactants and oils. The solvents having maximum solubility was selected for the microemulsion formulation. LAS (Linear Alkyl benzene Sulfonate), Span 80 and Almond oil were selected as Surfactant, co-surfactant and oil respectively. Micro-emulsion formulation was optimized using ternary phase diagram, globule size and percent transmittance. F1 and F43 formulations were optimized for Metformin and atorvastatin respectively. This optimized micro-emulsion was then utilized to form Emulgel. Lecithin and Sepineo P 600 was used as gelling agent for the formation of Emulgel. Emulgel was then evaluated for spreadability, viscosity and drug release. The optimized formula contained 3% sepineo P600 and 1% penetration enhancer i.e., Oleic acid. This optimized gel with good spreadability was further assessed for in-vivo wound healing activity using excision model. The results showed better wound healing for metformin gel compared to standard Betadine Ointment and Atorvastatin emulgel. Hence study concludes Metformin gel can be a promising therapy to treat Diabetic foot ulcer.

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INTRODUCTION

Approximately 170 million individuals are affected by diabetes worldwide, including 20.8 million in the USA, and by 2030 these numbers are projected to double. It is a major public health problem worldwide. Globally, the number of people with diabetes is expected to double between 2000 and 2030 while public awareness about this disease remains low. Diabetic wounds/ foot ulcers (DFUs) have a major impact on the patient as well as on the health care system. These ulcers tend to heal slowly, need intensive care and healing can be complicated by infection and gangrene, leading to long-term in-hospital treatment and/or amputation. The foot ulcer is a leading cause of hospital admissions for people with diabetes in the developed world and is a major morbidity associated with diabetes, often leading to pain, suffering, and a poor quality of life for patients. DFUs are estimated to occur in 15% of all patients with diabetes and precede 84% of all diabetes-related lower-leg amputations^[1].

Metformin Class III drug with anti-hyperglycemia property has been reported to increase angiogenesis and promote wound healing in diabetics. Angiogenesis is the physiochemical process which involves the growth of new blood vessels, from existing vessels, which leads for the restoration of blood flow to damage tissues, provides oxygen and nutrients that supports the growth and function of reparative cells^[2]. Atorvastatin the class II drug is a lipid-lowering agent, has been shown to accelerate the wound-healing process. It has broad-spectrum pleiotropic effects including anti-inflammatory, antioxidative, immune modulatory, antibacterial along with improvement of microvascular function and reperfusion^[3].

Gels are relatively the newer class of the dosage form and are widely been accepted as delivering the drug directly to the topical layer of the skin i.e. through stratum corneum, through sweat ducts or through the sebaceous follicles; from where it get absorbed into the blood circulation.^[4]

Hence an attempt has been made to develop separately Emulgels of Metformin and Atorvastatin. Metformin emulgel helps to improve the penetration of class III drug and Emulgel of Atorvastatin will help to increase solubility and bioavailability of the Class II drug in affected area of wound in diabetic patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Metformin HCL and Atorvastatin Calcium was purchased by Koprana Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai as gift sample. Span 80 was purchased by Evonik Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai, LAS was purchased by Colorcon Asia. Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai as gift sample, Sepenio P 600. oleic acid was purchased by Research Lab Fine Chem., Mumbai and almond oil was purchased by Hamdared Lab.

Selection of Excipients:

Screening of Excipients:

The solubility of both the drugs metformin and atorvastatin in various oils, surfactants and co-surfactants was determined by dissolving an excess amount of drugs in 1 mL of each of the selected oils, surfactants and co-surfactants in 5-mL stoppered vials separately. The mixture vials were then kept at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for stirring for 72 hours to attain equilibrium. The equilibrated samples were removed from the stirring and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant was taken and filtered through a membrane filter. The concentration of both the drugs was determined in the mixture respectively by UV spectrophotometer at their respective λ_{max} ^[5-7].

Formulation of Microemulsion Using Design Expert:

Formulations were developed using design expert mixture analysis model. Mixture analysis model is based on the considerations that the factors are ingredients of a mixture and the response is a function of proportions, not amount. Given these two conditions, fixing total facilities modeling of the response as a function of component proportions.

The three independent variables selected were Ratio of surfactant (X1), ratio of oil to surfactant mixture (X2) and type of drug (X3) (Table 1-2). The dependent variables are % transmission and globule size

Table 1 Factors and Levels for the Micro-emulsion Optimization.

Independent Variables	Factors	Level		
		-1	0	+1
X1	Ratio of surfactant to cosurfactant	1:2	1:1	2:1
X2	Ratio of oil to surfactant mixture	10:90	50:50	90:10
X3	Type of drug	Metformin	-	Atorvastatin
Dependent variables				
Y1	% transmission Metformin			
Y2	% transmission Atorvastatin			
Y3	Globule Size Metformin			
Y4	Globule size Atorvastatin			

Table 2 Composition of Metformin and Atorvastatin Micro-emulsion Formulations Respectively.

Run	Factor 1 A:Ratio of Surfactant to co surfactant	Factor 2 B:Ratio of Oil to surfactant mixture	Factor 3 C:Type of Drug	Run	Factor 1 A:Ratio of Surfactant to co surfactant	Factor 2 B:Ratio of Oil to surfactant mixture	Factor 3 C:Type of Drug
1	1:1	20:80	Met	23	1:1	70:30	Astat
2	1:1	10:90	Astat	24	2:1	90:10	Met
3	1:2	80:20	Astat	25	1:1	90:10	Met
4	2:1	50:50	Met	26	1:2	10:90	Met
5	2:1	40:60	Met	27	2:1	40:60	Astat
6	1:1	80:20	Met	28	2:1	80:20	Met
7	1:1	50:50	Astat	29	1:2	20:80	Met
8	1:1	90:10	Astat	30	1:1	60:40	Astat
9	1:2	60:40	Met	31	1:2	60:40	Astat
10	1:1	60:40	Met	32	1:1	30:70	Met
11	2:1	10:90	Met	33	1:2	40:60	Met
12	1:1	50:50	Met	34	1:1	70:30	Met
13	1:1	40:60	Astat	35	1:2	30:70	Astat
14	1:1	20:80	Astat	36	1:2	80:20	Met
15	2:1	70:30	Met	37	2:1	60:40	Met
16	2:1	90:10	Astat	38	1:2	40:60	Astat
17	2:1	30:70	Met	39	1:2	70:30	Met
18	2:1	70:30	Astat	40	1:2	90:10	Met
19	1:1	80:20	Astat	41	1:2	20:80	Astat
20	1:2	10:90	Astat	42	2:1	20:80	Met
21	1:2	50:50	Astat	43	1:1	30:70	Astat
22	2:1	10:90	Astat ⁱ				

Note: Met- Metformin, Astat- Atorvastatin.

Preparation of Microemulsion:

Firstly screening of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant for micro emulsion is carried out. Solubility of drug is investigated in different oils, surfactant and co-surfactants. A drug is dissolved in oil in which the drug has maximum solubility among the available, then surfactant and co-surfactant is added in which the drug has maximum solubility, mixed well and then water is added drop by drop and mixed well on magnetic stirrer to obtain a transparent microemulsion.^[8-10]

Evaluation of micro-emulsion^[8-10]:

Percentage transmittance:

Percentage transmittance of each sample was determined by using distilled water as reference.

Determination of the globule size:

The globule size of the micro-emulsion formulation can be determined by labmade Instruments.

Pseudo ternary Phase diagram:

The first step towards the formulation development was to determine the feasibility of the micro-emulsion formation. The boundaries of the micro-emulsion domains were determined with aid of pseudo ternary phase diagram. On the basis of the solubility studies, the combination of almond oil, span 80 and LAS (1:1) was selected as the oil phase. Distilled water was used as an aqueous phase. For the detailed study of the ternary phase diagrams were constructed using water titration method at ambient temperature. Water was added drop by drop, under gentle agitation, to each oily mixture until mixture become turbid.

In- vitro Drug Release :

The diffusion study is carried out on a modified Franz diffusion cell, with volume of 15mL. The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer pH 5.5. The donor compartment was fixed with cellophane membrane, containing the micro-emulsion formulations. At predetermined time intervals samples were withdrawn from the receptor compartment and analyzed for drug content, using a UV spectrophotometer at specific wavelength.

Drug Content :

Take 1ml of micro-emulsion. Dilute it with suitable solvent. Filter it to obtain clear solution. Absorbance was determined by using UV spectrophotometer. Standard plot of drug measured is prepared by same solvent after suitable dilution at respective wavelength in spectrophotometer.

Viscosity Measurements:

Viscosity of different micro-emulsion formulations was measured at 25 °C with a Brookfield viscometer with shear rate 50 rpm.

Determination of pH

The pH values for micro-emulsion were determined at 25 °C by pH meter.

Preparation of Emulgel:

First screening of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant for micro emulsion is carried out. Solubility of drug is investigated in different oils, surfactant and co-surfactants. A drug is dissolved in oil in which the drug has maximum solubility among the available, then surfactant and co-surfactant is added in which the drug has maximum solubility, mixed well then water is added drop by drop and mixed well on magnetic stirrer. Transparent micro-emulsion is formed. The optimized micro-emulsion was used further for the emulgel preparation of Metformin and Atorvastatin respectively. Then gelling agent is hydrated for overnight. The pH is adjusted around 6 to 6.5 using triethanolamine. For the preparation of emulgel, microemulsion and prepared gel are mixed in the appropriate ratio^[11-14].

Emulgel Optimization

The independent variables selected were Conc. of gelling agent (X1), Conc. of penetration enhancer (X2), type of gelling agent (X3), and type of penetration enhancer (X4). The dependent variables are viscosity (Y1), spreadability (Y2) and drug diffusion (Y3) as shown in table 3 and 4.

Table 3 Factors and Levels For Emulgel Formulations of Metformin and Atorvastatin Respectively

Independent Variables	Factors	level	
		-1	+1
X1	Conc of Gelling agent	1	5
X2	Conc of penetration enhancer	0.5	1.5
X3	Type of gelling agent	Sepineo	Lecithin
X4	Type of Penetration enhancer	Oleic acid	Urea
Dependent variables			
Y1	Viscosity		
Y2	Spreadability		
Y3	Drug Diffusion		

Table 4 Composition of Emulgel Formulations of Metformin and Atorvastatin Respectively.

Formulation	A: Conc of gelling agent	B: Conc of penetration enhancer	C: Type of gelling agent	D: Type of penetration enhancer
1	5	1.5	Sepineo	Oleic acid
2	1	0.5	Sepineo	urea
3	5	0.5	Lecithin	Oleic acid
4	1	0.5	Sepineo	urea
5	1	1.5	Lecithin	Oleic acid
6	5	0.7	Sepineo	urea
7	2.4	1.005	Lecithin	urea
8	1.6	1.5	Sepineo	urea
9	5	0.5	Lecithin	Oleic acid
10	1.7	0.5	Lecithin	Oleic acid
11	5	1.5	Lecithin	urea
12	1	1.5	Lecithin	Oleic acid
13	5	1.5	Sepineo	Oleic acid
14	3.04	0.914748	Sepineo	Oleic acid
15	5	1.5	Lecithin	urea

Evaluation of Emulgel^[14]**Physical Appearance:**

The prepared emulgel formulations are inspected visually for their colour and phase separation.

Particle size :

The particle size was determined using an optical microscope with software (PixelPro). The average particle size was expressed in terms of μm . The particle size was determined using an optical microscope. The microscope was fitted with a stage micrometer to calibrate the eyepiece micrometer.

Calibration of the eyepiece micrometer

One division of the stage micrometer = 0.01mm = 10 μm

$$C = (SM \times 10) / EM$$

Where; C = correction factor

SM = Reading of stage micrometer which coincides with reading of eye-piece micrometer (EM).

Measurement of pH :

The pH of various emulsified gel formulations was determined by using digital pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in 100ml distilled water and stored for two hours. The Measurement of pH of each formulations was done in triplicate and averages.

Swelling Index :

The swelling index can be calculated by placing specific amount of formulations on porous aluminum foil, it place in 0.1 N solution of NaOH solution then weight after specific time and calculated swelling index.

$$SW\% = [(Wt - W_0) / W_0] * 100$$

Wt = weight of swollen emulgel after time t.

W₀ = original weight of emulgel at zero time.

Spreadability study :

For the determination of spreadability, excess of formulation was placed between two glass slides and 100 g weight was placed on the upper glass slide for 5 min to compress the formulation to uniform thickness. Weight (140g) was added to the pan. The time in seconds require to separate the two slides was taken as a measure of spreadability.

$$\text{The spread } S = (M \times L) / T$$

S - Spreadability,

M - Weight tied to the upper slides (g),

L - Length of glass slide (cm), and

T - Time taken in seconds.

Rheological Study:

The viscosity of different emulsified gel formulation was determined at 37°C using a Brook field viscometer with helipad spindle.

Drug Content:

Take 1gm of emulgel. Mix it insuitable solvent. Filter it to obtain clear solution. Determine its absorbance using UV spectrophotometer. Standard plot of drug measured is prepared by same solvent after suitable dilution.

Differential scanning calorimeter:

Differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) was performed to determine the thermal behavior of Metformin and Atorvastatin respectively. Accurately weighed samples (2mg) were transferred to aluminum pans and sealed. All samples were run at a heating rate of 5°C/min over a temperature range of 30 to 360°C by using nitrogen gas as effluent gas and performed on Shimadzu DSC-60 thermal analyzer.

In-vivo study:**Experimental model:**

Alloxan monohydrate was weighed individually for each animal according to their body weight and solubilized with saline just prior to injection. Diabetes was induced by injecting it at a dose of 150 mg/kg body weight intraperitoneally. The animals were kept under observation and after 48 hrs blood glucose level was measured by One-touch glucometer. The diabetic rats (glucose level 200-300 mg/dl) were separated and divided into four different groups for experimental studies, with each group containing six animals

Experimental design:

The rats were divided into four groups each consist of six rats. Significant hyperglycemia was achieved within 48 hrs after alloxan (150 mg/kg body weight i.p) injection.

Group I- Control

Group II- Standard Betadine Ointment

Group III- Formulation 1 (Metformin Emulgel)

Group IV- Formulation 2 (Atorvastatin Emulgel)

Wound healing model in diabetic rats:

Animals:

Wistar albino rats of either sex (body wt. between 150-250 g) were used for the wound healing activity. They were housed in standard environmental conditions, fed with standard pellet diet and water ad libitum.

Induction of Diabetes:

Wistar albino Rats of either sex (150-250 g) were selected and maintained under standard laboratory conditions. Wound healing activity of emulgels was evaluated using alloxan induced diabetic rats. Experimental diabetes was induced by injecting alloxan monohydrate (150 mg/kg B.w) intraperitoneal route at 150 mg dissolved in (0.9%) normal saline to the fasted rats. The serum blood glucose levels were measured 3rd day after alloxan injection. The blood samples collection and estimation carried out as described under hypoglycemic activity.

Excision wound model:

In this model under light ether anesthesia a standard wound is made by cutting a circular skin in dorsal thoracic region of the experimental animals. Usually a wound of 500 mm² areas is made with the help of marking of margin on pre-shaved area with an indelible ink and rubber seal. Morton and Malone have described the evaluation of vulnerary activity of open wound in rats by planimetric measurements. It is also possible to study the phase of wound healing in this model. This is done by taking the photographs of the wounds at different time intervals in process of wound healing. Percentage closure of original wound after a predetermined lap at times (in days) is taken as parameter. Animals are kept in separate cages. The day on which wound was made consider as day '0' (Zero). Epithelialization period was noted as the number of days after wounding required for the Escher to fall off leaving no raw wound behind. Wound contraction rate was monitored by planimetric measurement of the wound area on 4th, 8th, 12th, 16th days. This was achieved by tracing the wound on a graph paper. Reduction in the wound area was expressed as percentage of the original size^[2,14].

Stability study

Stability study is carried out of an optimized formulation according to international conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The optimized batches of Emulgel were monitored up to 3 month at accelerated stability conditions of temperature and relative humidity (40⁰ ± 20C /75%± 5%RH). Samples were withdrawn after one month and characterized for Appearance, PH and viscosity. The choice of appropriate storage condition during accelerated stability study is necessary to predict the long term stability of Emulgel .

RESULT AND DISSCUSSION

Screening of Excipients

The most important criterion for screening of excipients is the solubility of the poorly soluble drug in oil, surfactants, and co-surfactants. The solubility of metformin and Atorvastatin respectively was found to be highest in 1:1 combination of span 80, LAS and almond oil as compared with other ratios of surfactant, co-surfactant and oil as shown in table 5 and 6 . Thus, these were selected as the oil phase for the development of the optimal formulation.

Table 5 Solubility study of Metformin and Atorvastatin in various Oils.

Oils	Solubility in mg/ml	
	Metformin	Atorvastatin
Almond Oil	65.08	111.20
Coconut oil	18.15	6.181

Table 6 Solubility study of Metformin and Atorvastatin in various Solvents.

Surfactant / Co-surfactant	Solubility in mg/ml	
	Metformin	Atorvastatin
Tween 80	19.75	3.49
LAS	226.25	400.0
Captex 200 P	25.06	4.4
Capmul	1856	16.872
PEG 600	16.05	11.85
Span 80	116.65	4000.0

Evaluation of Microemulsion: Globule size:

Table 7 ANOVA for response surface (Globule size).

Model	R2	Adjusted R2	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
2FI	0.9520	0.9407	<0.0001	1.04	84.25	Significant

Final equation in terms of coded factor :

$$\text{Globule Size} = +6.97 + 5.42 * B[1] + 2.96 * B[2] + 4.40 * B[3] + 2.88 * B[4] + 0.42 * B[5] + 0.053 * B[6] - 5.29 * B[7] - 5.40 * B[8]$$

Figure 1(a) represents the 3D Plot of Globule Size for Metformin Microemulsion, (b) represents the 3D Plot of Globule Size for and Atorvastatin Micro-emulsion.

A

b

From the above plots figure 1 a,b and anova analysis in table 7 it is observed that with increase in the concentration of surfactant in oil: surfactant mixture (Almond oil: Span80&LAS), the globule size slightly increases for the ratios 1:2 and 2:1 surfactant mixture than 1:1 ratio (Span 80:LAS), whereas, increase in surfactant mixture concentration, globule size decreases. Globule size is found to be minimum for equal concentration of oil:surfactant mixture

Also, with increases in oil concentration in oil:surfactant mixture, globule size decreases, for both the drugs. As addition of surfactants to these systems causes the interfacial film to stabilize and condense, while the addition of co-surfactant causes the film to expand; thus, the relative proportion of surfactant to co-surfactant has varied effects on the globule size.^[15]

PrecentTransmission:

Table 8 ANOVA for response surface (% transmission).

Model	R2	Adjusted R2	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
2F1	0.9636	0.9620	<0.0001	2.71	533.29	Significant

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors:

$$\% \text{ transmission} = +20.05 - 8.90 * A[1] + 18.62 * A[2]$$

Figure 2(a), (b) represents the 3D Plot of % transmission for Metformin and Atorvastatin Micro-emulsion respectively.

From the above plots figure 2a, b and table 8 it is observed that the % transmission is maximum for 1:1 ratio of surfactant mixture and maximum oil concentration in oil: surfactant mixture for both the drugs. % transmittance test is used to check dilutability and clarity of the sample. The transparency of a sample shows that there are no traces of undissolved drug or other solid ingredients. As the drug has highest solubility in the almond oil and surfactant mixture The high value of % transmittance indicates that the system iso-optically clear.^[16]

Pseudo ternary Phase diagram:

Although self-emulsification is a dynamic non-equilibrium process involving interfacial phenomena, information about the self-emulsification can be obtained using investigations of equilibrium phase behaviour. Emulsification efficiency of Oil-surfactant systems has been characterized and correlated with equilibrium phase diagrams.^[8]

Figure 3The pseudo-ternary phase diagrams of the oil-surfactant/cosurfactant mixture–water system at the 1:1, 1:2, and 2:1 respectively weight ratio of Almond oil /Span 80/ LAS at ambient temperature, dark area show microemulsion zone for Metformin Formulation

From the above ternary phase diagrams i.e., figure 3, it is observed that 1:1 ratio gives more microemulsion region .It is observed that with higher Percent of oil (Almond oil), emulsion becomes turbid. From this we found that oil in range of 60-70% and surfactant in range 60% can be used for optimized microemulsion.

Figure 4The pseudo-ternary phase diagrams of the oil-surfactant/co-surfactant mixture–water system at the 1:1, 1:2, and 2:1 respectively weight ratio of Almond oil /Span 80/ LAS at ambient temperature, dark area show micro-emulsions zone for Atorvastatin formul.

From the above ternary phase diagrams figure 4, it is observed that 1:1 ratio gives more microemulsion region. It is observed that with higher Percent of oil (Almond oil), emulsion becomes turbid. From this we found that oil in range of 70-80 % and surfactant in range 50% can be used for optimized microemulsion. The phase diagrams clearly indicated that microemulsion existence region increased with increase in the weight ratio of surfactant/cosurfactant.

Characterization of Microemulsion:

Table 9 Microemulsion formulation Characterization.

Formulation	Drug content mg/ml	Viscosity cps	%Drug Diffusion in 120minutes	Formulation	Drug content mg/ml	Viscosity cps	%Drug diffusion in 120minutes
F1	92.22	580.23	85.22	F23	32.4	486.16	69.00
F2	29.54	470.25	65.35	F24	10.636	495.25	82.26
F3	55.25	435.12	74.05	F25	4.90	512.14	81.05
F4	70.56	550.13	68.86	F26	13.54	564.25	66.020
F5	59.09	520.25	82.26	F27	18.09	456.65	82.023
F6	41.45	575.26	76.02	F28	12.45	544.25	66.12
F7	59.63	473.12	68.10	F29	8.36	523.15	65.95
F8	22.72	445.22	85.03	F30	13.81	576.35	59.23
F9	28.81	565.55	69.26	F31	28.90	453.45	66.45
F10	28	453.62	66.45	F32	12	486.26	66.88
F11	15.27	464.86	74.56	F33	10.36	496.25	76.32
F12	10.36	457.45	82.16	F34	9.45	582.45	68.65
F13	9.45	458.56	65.63	F35	2.54	520.62	81.06
F14	2.54	542.85	83.23	F36	16.18	524.15	63.15
F15	49.45	533.25	60.35	F37	41.45	561.21	66.15
F16	39.50	564.35	66.12	F38	57027	543.22	65.45
F17	52.03	554.15	75.26	F39	22.72	582.23	68.95
F18	15.27	494.16	82.23	F40	28.81	576.29	67.62
F19	23.83	549.18	66.26	F41	45.23	573.25	66.12
F20	39.50	523.45	65.02	F42	66.12	550.46	66.45
F21	33	415.25	66.05	F43	89.45	590.25	73.21
F22	28.01	423.25	74.06				

Table 10 Optimized Micro-emulsion as per Design Expert.

Factor	Name	Metformin Microemulsion	Atorvastatin Microemulsion
A	Ratio of Surfactant to co surfactant	1:1	1:1
B	Ratio of Oil to surfactant mixture	20:80	30:70
C	Type of Drug	Met	Astat

Depending upon the globule size, %transmittance and ternary phase diagram the optimize microemulsion formulation F1 and F43 was selected for the further emulgel formulations as shown in table 10.

Optimization of Metformin and Atorvastatin Emulgel Formulation:

SPREADABILITY:

Table 11 ANOVA for response surface (Spread ability).

Emulgel	Model	R2	Adjusted R2	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
Metformin Emulgel	2FI	0.9956	0.9938	<0.0001	0.31	560.90	Significant
Atorvastatin Emulgel	2FI	0.9951	0.9931	<0.0001	0.98s	503.14	Significant

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors: Metformin Emulgel

$$\text{Spreadability} = +29.27 + 2.14*A - 3.73*B - 0.49*C + 0.88*D$$

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors: Atorvastatin Emulgel

$$\text{Spreadability} = +22.49 + 6.25* A - 4.67* B + 7.92* C + 7.06* D$$

Figure 5 3D Plot for Spreadability of Metformin.

Figure 6 3D Plot for Spreadability of Atorvastatin.

From the above plot figure 5 and 6 it is observed that as the concentration of gelling agent increases the spreadability of the formulations increases for both the drugs. This may be due to self emulsifying ability of sepineo P600 used with almond oil.¹⁷

VISCOSITY:

Table 12 ANOVA for response surface (Viscosity).

Drug	Model	R2	Adjusted R2	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
Metformin Emulgel	2F1	0.9978	0.9969	<0.0001	0.041	1130.47	Significant
Atorvastatin Emulgel	2FI	0.9946	0.9924	<0.0001	0.044	457.40	Significant

Figure 7 3D Plot for Viscosity of Atorvastatin.

Figure 8 3D Plot for Viscosity of Metformin.

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors: Atorvastatin Emulgel

$$\text{Viscosity} = +3.33 + 0.30 * A + 0.42 * B + 0.031 * C + 0.082 * D$$

As shown in figure 7 and 8 the viscosity of the emulgel formulation was found to be increase with increase in the concentration of penetration enhancer and gelling agent. It is due to the presence of water, sepineo P600 reverses and the polymer network deploys instantly, forming a perfectly stable gel. The viscosity of the medium increases until the consistency of a perfectly stable cream-gel is obtained. Sepineo P600 is an essential thickening agent It is easy to used as it does not require neutralization or rehydration when developing gel.¹⁸

DRUG RELEASE:

Table 13 ANOVA for response surface (Drug diffusion) of Metformin Emulgel.

Model	R2	Adjusted R2	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
2F1	0.9902	0.9863	<0.0001	0.14	252.10	Significant

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors:

$$\text{Drug Diffusion} = +3.57 - 0.41 * A + 0.57 * B - 0.032 * C - 1.01 * D$$

Figure 9 3D plot for Drug diffusion of Metformin Emulgel.

From the above 3D plot figure 9 it was observed that the Drug release rate of the formulation was not affected by the incorporation of permeation enhancer (oleic acid). As it is generally agreed that *in vitro* drug release data for transdermal formulations cannot be used to accurately predict permeation across the skin, due to the barrier properties of the stratum corneum which can be altered by the composition of vehicle or the presence of various permeation enhancers in the formulation Also the drug diffusion of the formulation containing sepineo P600 as a gelling agent is found to increased viscosity due to the increase in hydrophilicity of the emulgel which is due to theacrylamide/sodium acryloyl dimethyl taurate copolymer group in sepineo having self-emulsifying ability and also form a stable emulgel.^[17,18]

DRUG RELEASE

Table 14 ANOVA for response surface (DRUG DIFFUSION) of Atorvastatin Emulgel.

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	P value	S.D	F value	Remark
2FI	0.9941	0.9918	<0.0001	0.054	423.92	Significant

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors:

$$\text{Drug Diffusion} = +1.35 + 0.43 * A - 0.063 * B - 0.43 * C - 0.19 * D$$

Figure 10 3D plot for Drug diffusion of Atorvastatin Emulgel.

The *in-vitro* release of the emulgel formulation increases in the presence of penetration enhancer (Oleic acid) as shown in figure 10. As oleic acid is used as the permeation enhancer in the formulation it interacts with stratum corneum lipids and disrupts their structure, increases their fluidity, and consequently increases permeation.^{19,20}

OPTIMIZED FORMULA AS PER DESIGN EXPERT

Table 15 Optimized Formula of Metformin and Atorvastatin Emulgel.

Factor	Name	Metformin	Atorvastatin
A	Conc. of gelling agent	3.00	3.00
B	Conc. of penetration enhancer	1.00	1.00
C	Type of gelling agent	Sepineo	Sepineo
D	Type of penetration enhancer	Oleic acid	Oleic acid

Evaluation of Optimized Emulgel Formulation of Metformin and Atorvastatin.

Table 16 Characterization of optimized emulgel.

Formulation	Physical Appearance	pH	Swelling index	Spreadability	Viscosity	Drug Content	Globule size
Metformin Emulgel	Cream colour	5.7	94	54.12	1539.70	94.25	12.25
Atorvastatin Emulgel	Cream colour	5.9	92	56.41	1643.28	95.86	10.43

Differential Scanning Calorimetry(DSC) of Optimized Formulations:

Figure 11 DSC of AtorvastatinEmulgel.

DSC studies were carried out to confirm compatibility between drug and excipients. The thermal behaviour of drug and formulations were studied. In the thermogram(Figure11), the drug showed a endothermic peak (at 84.52⁰c) which shows the shifts of drug peak might be due to dispersion in SMEDDS and gelling agent.

Figure 12 DSC of Metformin emulgel.

DSC studies were carried out to confirm compatibility between drug and excipients. The thermal behaviour of drug and formulations were studied. In the thermogram (figure 12), the drug showed an endothermic peak (at 102^oc) which shows the shifts of drug peak might be due to dispersion in SMEDDS and gelling agent.

IN-VIVO STUDY FOR EMUGEL

GLUCOSE LEVEL ESTIMATION:

The rats' serum glucose levels which were over and above 200 mg/dl were considered to be diabetic hence they were selected and divided into four groups of six rats' each (Table 17).

Table 17 Effect of Metformin and Atorvastatin Emulgel on wound contraction and wound healing activity.

Treatment n=6	% healing effect on Wound contraction on different days				Epithelisation day
	4 th day	8 th days	12 th day	18 th day	
Group I- Control	3.03±0.32	6.36±1.48	12.78±0.84	18.30±2.18	25 days
Group II-Standard	20.03±1.27***	43.12±3.08***	51.21±2.86***	73.2±2.26***	14 days
Group III-Metformin Emulgel Formulation	21.21±2.45***	44.86±2.33***	68.23±2.86***	87.34±2.28***	10 days
Group III-Atorvastatin Emulgel Formulation	17.75±3.43**	26.28±2.11***	42.11±2.486***	53.21±1.53***	15 days

Values are the mean ± S.E.M. of 4 rats/treatment. Significance *** p<0.001, **p <0.01 with compared to control group.

Figure 13 Effect of Metformin and Atorvastatin Emulgel on wound contraction on 4th and 18th day.

The percentage of wound contraction (Table 13) in the Metformin emulgel was found to be higher and statistically significant as compared to control, marketed Betadine ointment and Atorvastatin emulgel on the 4th day, 8th day, 12th day, and 18th day.

Stability Study:

The optimized formulations were subjected to stability studies according to ICH guidelines by storing at 40 °C/75% RH for 3 months. These samples were analyzed and checked for changes in physical appearance, particle size, entrapment efficiency and drug release at 0, 1, 2 and 3 months. The obtained data is presented in Table.18 From the table, it is clear that the formulation did not undergo any chemical changes/interaction during the study period.

Table 18 Stability Data.

Sr. No.	Formulations	Parameter		1 month	2 month	3 month
1	Atorvastatin	Physical Appearance	White creamy	No change	No change	No change
2		Drug content	94±0.74%	94%	94%	93%
3		pH	5.5	5.5	5.5	6
4		Spreadability	30	30	29	27
1	Metformin	Physical Appearance	White creamy	No change	No change	No change
2		Drug content	90%	90%	89%	89%
3		pH	5.5	5.5	5.4	5.8
4		Spreadability	28	28	26	26

CONCLUSION

Development Emulgel for wound healing can achieve better patient compliance and better patient acceptability due to localized delivery of wound healing drugs to the wounds is more convenient than systemic administration as higher concentrations of the medication are delivered directly to the desired area in a sustained manner.

The results showed better wound healing for metformin gel compared to standard Betadine Ointment and Atorvastatin emulgel. Hence study concludes Metformin gel can be a promising therapy to treat Diabetic foot ulcer. In future an attempt can be made to combine both the drugs and evaluate it for Wound healing activity for its synergistic effect.

Conflict of Interest:

No Conflict of Interest

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